

A study of Bacteria Neisseria Meningitidis which causes meningococcal disease

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Abstract

Meningococcal meningitis is bacterial meningitis, a severe infection of the thin membranes surrounding the brain and spinal cord. Meningococcal meningitis is associated with high case mortality (up to 50% when untreated) and severe sequelae frequency (more than 10%). Therefore, early antibiotic treatment is the primary measure available to save lives and reduce complications. Meningococcal meningitis is observed worldwide but lies within the meningitis belt, extending from Africa. sub-Saharan Africa from Senegal in the west to the east of Ethiopia is the heaviest burden of the disease. About 30,000 cases are still reported each year in this area which shows an incalculable potential danger to humankind in the 21st century.

1. General

1.1. Genus: Neisseria, Trevisan, 1885

1.1.1. Intro

Neisseria is a large genus of bacteria that colonize the mucosal surfaces of many animals. Of the 11 species colonized by humans, only two are pathogens, *N. meningitidis*, and *N. gonorrhoeae*. This genus in family Neisseriaceae of parasitic bacteria grow in pairs and sometimes tetrads and grow best at 98.6°F (37°C) in animal or serum media.

1.1.2. Genome

The best-studied species is *N. Meningitidis*, with more than seventy strains. In contrast, the least studied species is *N. Gonorrhoeae*, with only ten strains. All of their genomes were sequenced entirely.

1.2. Neisseria Meningitidis

1.2.1. General information

Neisseria Meningitidis belongs to the kingdom (regnum) Bacteria, phylum Proteobacteria, class Beta Proteobacteria, order (ordo) Neisseriaceae, family (familia) Neisseriaceae, genus (genus) *Neisseria*, species (species) *N. Meningitidis*, whose short name is Meningococcus.

1.2.2. Characteristics

A gram-negative bacterium that is diplococci (as shown) can infect only humans and has never been isolated from animals because it cannot obtain iron from any other than humans (transferrin and lactoferrin).

- Genome size: 2,184,406 bp
- Number of genes: 2049

1.2.3. Classify

Neisseria meningitidis is most likely to cause major epidemics. To date, 12 serogroups of *Neisseria meningitidis* have been identified, 6 of which are known to cause epidemics (A, B, C, W135, X, and Y). The geographical distribution and pathogenicity vary from group to group.

1.2.4. Type of toxin

N. meningitidis is an endotoxin due to lipopolysaccharide (LPS), a bacterial cell wall component. The other toxin is the polysaccharide of the cyst, which inhibits the phagocytosis of the host's immune response, and fimbriae play a role in helping bacteria adhere to the epithelial cells of the nose and throat.

A super toxin-producing strain was discovered in China. The effects of this toxin are still being determined, and no definitive results are available.

2. Details

2.1. Mechanism of inheritance

2.1.1. Gene expression strategy

N. meningitidis is transmitted via respiratory droplets leading to invasion of the nasopharynx. In rare cases, meningococcal blood and cerebrospinal fluid transmission leads to meningitis and/or sepsis. To effectively colonize their respective niches in the human host, *N. meningitidis* must successfully compete with important resident flora for space and nutrients and evade conservation host immune defense. This, therefore, requires an ability to rapidly sense and respond to a wide variety of environmental stimuli. At the most basic level, this requires modulation of gene expression when the circumstances call for it. The following is a discussion of the mechanisms of bacterial gene regulation with a particular focus on the strategies used by pathogenic *Neisseria* to control gene expression of factors that play a role in *Neisseria*'s pathogenesis. Topics will include using alternative sigma factors, the regulation of positive and negative gene transcription by specific transcription factors, and adaptation through the accumulation of random spontaneous mutations over time in chromosomal DNA. In addition, some discussions will focus on emerging gene regulation mechanisms such as post-transcriptional regulation through small RNA molecules.

2.1.2. Chemical properties

N. meningitidis can grow anaerobically and/or bacteria by anaerobic respiration, using two enzymes central to the denitrification pathway. Nitrite reductase (AniA) converts nitrite to nitric oxide (NO), then reduce to nitrogen oxide by nitric oxide reductase (NorB). The regulation of the expression of *aniA* and *norB* is complex, involving multiple transcriptional activators and/or repressors. Transcription of *aniA* occurs only when oxygen concentrations are low due to the absolute requirement for FNR, an oxygen-sensitive transcriptional activator. In the presence of nitrite, it is converted to nitric oxide by AniA, leading to inactivation of the inhibitor, NsrR, and proportional reduction and NarP-dependent activation. Three repressors, NsrR, Fur and ArsR control Expression of *norB*. Replication of *norB* can occur aerielly in the presence of nitric oxide, due to inactivation of NsrR. Fur and ArsR compete for overlapping binding sites; Fur + iron displaces ArsR, causing further distortion of *norB*. In addition to allowing growth under oxygen-restricted conditions, the denitrification pathway can alter nitric oxide levels during infection, leading to altered NF- κ B activation and suppression of the immune response . When a long half-life NO donor is added to mimic host NO production, gonococci reduce NO from inflammatory states ($>1 \mu\text{M}$) to anti-inflammatory steady-state concentrations (100-200 nM)). In the presence of nitrite, most strains produced stable high levels of NO, while strains requiring arginine, hypoxanthine and uracil (AHU) set steady-state levels $<1 \mu\text{M}$. In meningococcus, the presence of a denitrification pathway protects bacteria against the toxic effects of reactive nitrogen species and alters macrophages' cytokine production profile.

2.1.3. Genomes and Recombinants

Analyzes of the available genome sequences of *Neisseria* species and strains have greatly increased our knowledge of the recombination processes occurring in this genus. The accumulation of multiple copies of genetic factors such as insertion sequences and bacteria contributed to the genomic diversity. However, these factors also serve as substrates for homologous recombination reactions that, at low frequencies, have resulted in different genome rearrangements. Many examples of horizontal acquisition of DNA segments are also evident. The largest of these obtained DNA segments are the Horizontal Islands and appear to have been acquired at low frequency through an unknown process. second class of horizontally acquired DNA segments, consisting of smaller fragments known as Minimally Movable Elements, appears to move through the bacterial population with higher frequency. These elements consist of a series

of mutually exclusive cassettes, including only a few genes, that target specific locations on the genome. It is still under research how these elements evolved, but their movement appears to be facilitated by a natural variation system, and integration occurs through homologous recombination involving flanking genes conserve. Each sequenced genome also contains a significant number of non-coding repetitive DNA sequences. The most common of these repeats is related to gene-specific DNA recognition and uptake during transformation. The repeats others appear to be targets for site-specific recombination or, especially when occurring in repeating arrays, homologous recombination systems. Finally, genomic sequencing has also revealed numerous genes that appear to be altered by phase or antigenicity. Although the systems that act on a few of these genes have been known for some time, the magnitude of the gene variables repertoire is much larger than expected.

2.2. Interaction with host cells

2.2.1. Pathogenic adhesion strategy

N. meningitidis has evolved many surface contact proteins that mediate interactions with host. Pathogen interactions are a multifactorial process. Several surface structures have been proved to play a role in this process, which suggests interactions mediated by different molecules are important in determining tissue tropism and invasiveness versus transport potential. Porins, type IV pili, and protein opacity are major objects of study in pathogenesis, and recent studies have improved our understanding of their function at the level of molecular detail. In the last few years, the availability of neisserial genome sequencing has enabled the identification of novel surface proteins with potential roles as binders and virulence factors. The characterization of these novel proteins has expanded our knowledge of many of the strategies developed by pathogenic *Neisseriae* to infect the host.

2.2.2. Mechanism of cell invasion

Neisseria meningitidis is an extracellular human-specific pathogen responsible for bacteremia and meningitis. As like most bacterial pathogens, *N. meningitidis* exploits host cell signaling pathways to promote its uptake by host cells. *N. meningitidis* has neither a type III nor a type IV secretion system. The signals leading to bacterial colonization are induced by type IV pili, the key property that mediates bacterial adhesion to cells. Signals induced following type IV

pilus-mediated adhesion are responsible for forming microvilli-like structures at the bacterial cell-interaction site. These microvilli trigger the internalization of bacteria inside the cells. The major consequence of these signaling events is that actin cytoskeleton reorganization leads to forming a protruding membrane engulfing bacterial pathogens into the intracellular vacuole. The efficient internalization of *N. meningitidis* also requires activating an alternative signaling pathway and the tyrosine kinase receptor ErbB2. Besides type IV pili, other outer membrane proteins may be involved in other mechanisms of bacterial entry into the cell.

2.3. Main reaction

2.3.1. Bacterial innate immunity

The current pattern in neisserial infection is that these pathogens have diverse, diverse cell surfaces. One of the functions of this variation is to allow them to avoid actions that kill the innate immune system. of the host. In this chapter, scientists will define important features of the innate immune system related to neuropathology, examining the role of *N. meningitidis* modified cell surface antigens. in eliciting responses from different host cells and providing some insights into the molecular basis of the disease. Will describe the features required on bacteria to initiate colonization in different anatomical sites and sexes and examine how the host responds to these colonization events. (Disease versus asymptomatic colonies). Finally, they will look at the molecular mechanisms by which innate immune system cells are activated and how different activation mechanisms could lead to different disease outcomes.

2.3.2. Additional interactions

Neisseria meningitidis has developed complex mechanisms to evade extermination using the complement system. Binding to complement inhibitors, LOS sialylation, and cystic polysaccharide expression in the case of *N. meningitidis* all play key roles in allowing these bacteria to evade complement. The variety of additional evasion strategies reflects the importance of overcoming the immune barrier. Neisserial resistance to complement mediated killing appears to be limited in humans and may explain the host specificity of neisserial disease. Recent advances in our understanding of neisserial complement evasion strategies will aid in the development of better animal models and vaccine design.

3. Related diseases

3.1. Harm

The greatest harm recorded is causing meningococcal disease in humans. Bacteria are present in the nasopharynx in 5-15% of adults. Meningitis is the only form that can cause fluid formation.

The bacteria are transmitted through human saliva and respiratory secretions through movements such as coughing, kissing and biting children's toys. Early symptoms of the disease are fatigue, then sudden changes to fever, headache, stiff neck leading to coma and finally death. These symptoms are easily confused with other inflammatory diseases caused by other organisms like *Haemophilus influenzae* or *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Mortality is about 10% of cases. People with weakened immune systems are particularly at risk for meningococcal infection. For example, people with kidney failure or a splenectomy. Therefore, the vaccine is given to people whose spleens are inactive or have to be removed.

Suspected cases of meningitis are a medical emergency and require immediate medical intervention. Current guidance for doctors in the UK for suspected meningococcus or bacteremia is to give antibiotics intravenously (could be penicillin or cefotaxime) and hospitalize the patient. Unfortunately, this also means it is more difficult to identify *Neisseria meningitidis* in the laboratory, as antibiotics will reduce the number of bacteria present in the body. This guideline is based on the idea that the ability to determine the presence of bacteria is less valuable than reducing mortality.

Sepsis caused by *Neisseria meningitidis* receives less public attention than meningococcal meningitis even when the cause of bacteremia is infant mortality. Meningococcus bacteremia usually presents with typical symptoms of a broad rash that does not discolor when pressed with a glass object and does not cause typical symptoms such as meningitis. That means this early symptom is easy to miss, and the risk of death is close to 50% within hours of these early signs. Many health associations advise people who see a rash that doesn't discolor to go to the emergency room as soon as possible. Not all cases of widespread rash are meningococcal bacteremia; Other possibilities should also be considered (eg, ITP a disease of platelets or Henoch-Schönlein purpura).

Complications of the disease include Waterhouse-Friderichsen syndrome (very heavy bleeding usually in both adrenal glands caused by acute meningococcus bacteremia), adrenal insufficiency, and disseminated intravascular coagulation.

3.2. Infected target

Anyone can be infected. Some subjects are at high risk of infection:

- Infants under one year old
- Adolescents and young adults between 16 and 23 years old
- People with certain medical conditions that affect the immune system
- Microbiologists frequently work with isolates of *N. meningitidis*
- People are at risk of disease when there is an outbreak of disease in their population.

3.3. Treatment and prevention

3.3.1. Treatment

Patients diagnosed with *N. meningitidis* infection should be hospitalized immediately and treated with antibiotics (penicillin G, ceftriaxone, and cefotaxime) and supportive care. Studies show that the use of corticosteroids does not work.

3.3.2. Prevention

All contacts of the patient 7 days before the onset of illness should receive antibiotics (rifampin, ceftriaxone, or ciprofloxacin) to prevent infection. This is especially the case in the case of children and caregivers or nannies who are in contact with the patient and anyone potentially exposed through high-risk activities such as kissing, sharing household items, etc. , or medical interventions such as artificial respiration. In addition, anyone who regularly eats, sleeps, or stays at the patient's home in the 7 days before the onset of illness or who sits next to the patient on a flight of 8 hours or more should be given preventive medication.

There are currently two main vaccines used in the United States to prevent meningococcus. The double vaccine (MCV4) was licensed in the United States in 2005. This vaccine is for use in people 2 to 55 years of age. The polysaccharide vaccine (MPSV4) has been in circulation since the 1970s and is used if MCV4 is ineffective and

intended for people over 55 years of age. Information on groups of people who should be vaccinated is available from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

Conclusion

Meningococcal disease has a significant impact on human health. Therefore, it is necessary to fully vaccinate to prevent the invasion of this bacteria. In particular, it is necessary to have periodic health checks, plan treatment and strictly follow medical regulations for disease prevention and treatment. WHO has been recommending the organization to set the alarm level of this disease to the highest level in recent years.

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